

Western Zhou (1045 BCE - 771 BCE)

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Entry tags: Chinese State Religion, Confucian (rujia 儒家) Traditions, Daoist Traditions, Divination, Religious Group, Eurasian religious practices, Shamanism, Assyrian Religions, Sanxingdui, Bön (Tibetan: bon), Technology, Nationalism, Early Bronze Age, Secularism, Indigenous tribal, Japanese Religions, Korean Religions, Divination, Sichuan Basin and Hanzhong Valley Region, Levantine Religion, Mesoamerican Religions, Mongolian Religions, Syncretic Religions, Southeast Asian Religions, Military Cults, Sichuan, Classical Indo-European, Indo-European Religion, Confucianism, Animist, Language, Turkic, Asia Minor, Religious Practice, Early Chinese cosmology, Early Chinese cosmogony, Early Chinese Traditions, Regional Religious System, State Religion, Babylonian Religions, Indo-European, Inner Asian Native Religions, Chinese Religion, geomancy, Chinese Common Religions, Chinese Folk Religions, Sino-Tibetan, Sinitic, Classical-Middle-Modern Sinitic

Recording the state of our knowledge in March-April 2024, this entry on Western Zhou (circa 1045/1046 BCE - 771 BCE) examines the best/most creditable known primary and secondary sources (including archaeological, literary, and artistic evidence), data analysis, and approaches to and interpretations of the subject matter. As a key part of the three dynasties in Chinese history—legendary, real, imagined and unimagined—the Xia (夏, circa 2070 BCE - 1600 BCE), Shang (商, aka Yin 殷, circa 1600 BCE - 1046 BCE), and Zhou of early China, the Western Zhou (西周 circa 1046/1045 BCE - 771 BCE) began with King Wu of the Zhou in the “West” who toppled the last king of the Shang, and ended when Marquess of Shen (申) allegedly joined other tribal groups such as Quanrong (犬戎) took over the Zhou capital Hao and killed King You of the Zhou in 771 BCE, forcing the Zhou royal court to relocate (out of the Wei river valley near today’s Xi’an area in Shaanxi Province) eastward to Luoyang, a strategic settlement/basin on the Yellow River in present Henan Province. In transmitted oral and written accounts especially some core texts of Confucius (551-479 BCE), the Western Zhou has been regarded highly as the “model” of ideal governance and social harmony in early China. (Li, 2006, p. 1; Wilkinson, 2012, pp. 688-702) What is “China” then? “Loosely defined, it [China] refers to the territory encompassed today by the People’s Republic of China. But the original part of China where Chinese characters were written circa 1200 B.C.E. was a small region some 200 kilometers (125 miles) across. ... China’s area grew and changed as surrounding peoples with different cultures and languages were defeated or absorbed.” (Hansen, 2015, pp. 3-4) The very topic of Western Zhou (circa 1046/1045 BCE - 771 BCE) also invites us living in the twenty-first century to be aware of the meaning of some key terms, religion, Chinese, non-Chinese, foreign, foreigners, the Hans, and the non-Hans, while unpacking racial nationalism, Han Chinese nationalism and sino-centrism /exceptionalism in ideological narratives, through written and archaeological records (Cheng, 2017; Marks, 2012; Wang, 2023; Wang, 2020). Religion, for instance, denotes the “belief in the existence of a god or gods, and the activities that are connected with the worship of them, or in the teachings of a spiritual leader.”

(<https://www.oxfordlearnersdictionaries.com/definition/english/religion?q=religion>) Generally speaking, the Western Zhou religion can be characterized mainly in the following three aspects: First, the Western Zhou shared with its predecessor, the Shang, a belief in a High God (Shangdi 上帝), ancestor worship, and divination that embodied the will of spirits and deities, although there was a lesser degree or even replacement of those practices as the Western Zhou developed. Second, the High God of the Shang slowly receded into the idea of heaven (tian 天), an abstract superbeing or overlord, and mandate of heaven (a kind of divine destiny in East Asian contexts) that justified rulership and switchover of rulers in the Western Zhou. Third, divination in the Western Zhou took places in various forms that might and/or might not have overlapped with the Shang oracle bones’ practices. Transmitted classics, The Book of Changes, the Book of Documents, and the Book of Rites, have been widely considered a reflection of the Western Zhou religion.

In historiography, “classical” modern scholarly works on the Western Zhou are probably mainly manifest in the modern fascination with Confucianism and Daoism, the early translations by James Legge and others, a sort of foundational trend that ran through the 19th-century sinology. Archaeological research on the Zhou arose in the 1920s alongside the excavations of Shang sites and generated considerable interest among Christian missionaries, scholars, art dealers, and others alike. Apart from artistic dimensions (e.g. bronze cauldrons), the evolution of the Chinese written language from oracle bones via bronze inscriptions to the post-Qin forms became a focus of attention, adding a linguistic layer to the understanding of the artifacts, with Bernhard Karlgren as a most prolific scholar. Although generic thematic overviews on the Zhou period as part of China’s longer history abound, some research, e.g. by Friedrich Hirth, are dedicated to the history of the period in itself. One can find some trends and approaches to understanding the Western Zhou in the material listed in bibliography at the end. Most prominently are statecraft (Creel, Falkenhausen, Li), archaeology and artifacts (Shelach-Lavi, Chang, Rawson, Hsu), ritual and society (Khayutina, Cao & Chen, Rawson), socio-geographical perspectives (Flad & Chen, Li), diverse and ordinary people’s lives and voices (Hansen, 2015), and long-term trajectory methodologies (Shelach and Jaffe, 2014). The Western Zhou was drawn into S. N. Eisenstadt’s global argument about “axial age civilizations,” through Mark Elvin, Tu Weiming and Cho Xun-hsu’ contributions, which describe the emergence of 天 during early (Western) Zhou as a divine principle that links the Zhou up with Hellenic-Judaic-Christian (and Indic) cultures during the Axial Age, an argument that explicitly links cultural, geographical and developmental similarity during long periods of antiquity, or in today’s words, international/global/world history. Lately, there have been some distinct approaches and metallic data analysis of the Western Zhou as seen in Hansen 2015 and Y.-K. Hsu, R. O’Sullivan and H. Li, 2021. Critical of the prevailing “dynastic cycle” or “traditional court historian” model of viewing history, Valerie Hansen’s 2015 book breaks dynastic periodization by dividing imperial Chinese history into three phases: Inventing China (1250 BCE – 200 CE), Facing West (200 CE – 1000 CE), and Facing North (1000 – 1800) in hopes of bringing out more diverse and ordinary voices of peoples living in Chinas. Making use of published lead isotope data from artefacts and ore bodies, Hsu 2021 reveals the dynamic circulation of metal within the Zhou domains and its transportation network with neighboring regions particularly in metalliferous districts in the Yangtze area.

Date Range: 1045 BCE - 771 BCE

Region: Western Zhou (based on Li Feng)

Region tags: East Asia, Asia

Based on maps found in Li Feng's *Landscape and Power* (2009).

参与者情况：

✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

来源

帮助理解这一问题的书面资料：

– Source 1: Wu, Chucai (吴楚材), and Wu Diaohou (吴调侯), compiled. *Guwen Guanzhi* [古文观止]. 1959 ed. 2 vols. Beijing: Zhonghua shuju, 1982.

– Source 1: Wilhelm, Hellmut, and Cary F. Baynes. *The I Ching or Book of Changes*. Bollingen Series (General) V.V. 19. Princeton: Princeton University Press, 1967.

– Source 2: Minford, John, and Joseph M. S. Lau, eds. *Classical Chinese Literature, vol. 1: From Antiquity to the Tang Dynasty*. New York and Hong Kong: Columbia University Press and Hong Kong University Press, 2000.

– Source 3: Sima, Qian. Annotated by Pei Yin (between 420–479 CE). *Shiji: Zhou benji disi*. Beijing:

Zhonghua shuju, 1999, 1st ed. in 1959.

帮助理解这一问题的在线资料:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.chinesewords.org/>
- Source 1 Description: Hanyuwang (漢語網)
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.arteducation.com.tw/guwen/>
- Source 2 Description: Zhonghua gushiwen guji shujiwang (中華古詩文古書籍網)
- Source 1 URL: <http://www.chinaknowledge.de/History/Zhou/zhou-event-xizhou.html>
- Source 1 Description: ChinaKnowledge.de: An Encyclopaedia on Chinese History, Literature and Art by Dr. Ulrich Theobald

相关的在线的原始文本资料库(使用原语言和/或翻译)

- Source 1 URL: <https://ctext.org/zhushu-jinian/zhs>
- Source 1 Description: Simplified characters of Zhushu jinian 《竹书纪年》
- Source 2 URL: <https://ctext.org/zhushu-jinian/zh>
- Source 2 Description: Complex characters of Zhushu jinian 《竹書紀年》 [戰國 (公元前475年 - 公元前221年)]
- Source 3 URL: <https://ctext.org/zh>
- Source 3 Description: Zhonghua zhexueshu dianzihua jihua (中國哲學書電子化計劃)

一般变量

成员/团体互动

其他宗教团体与该宗教之间有文化上的接触吗：

– Yes

Notes: Hook, 1991, pp. 68-90

↳ 这种文化接触是竞争性的吗：

– Yes

Notes: Hook, 1991, pp. 68-90, esp. pp. 75-77: "A major problem in dealing with China's past is to define who were the 'Chinese' and what area can be considered as 'China' at any given period. ... The problem is further complicated by the fact that archaeology is making it clear that 'Chinese' culture did not derive from any single group of people, but evolved in a number of different centres." (p. 75)

↳ 文化接触是兼容并包/多元的吗：

– Yes

Notes: Yes and No, depending which time period and kings (12 of them) of the Western Zhou are at issue.

↳ 文化接触是中立的吗：

– No

↳ (在采样地区内)有暴力冲突吗：

– Yes

Notes: During the Western Zhou and within the sample region, there were many violent conflicts. The Zhou were a nomadic and/or semi-nomadic clan from the northwestern fringe of central China/the Central Plain (Zhongyuan 中原). The violence of the Western Zhou culture is evident in campaigns and hunts with many human victims/sacrifices/captives, often decapitated, in tombs and among buildings. Military conflicts often broke out between/within the Zhou royal house and its regional rulers/relatives. In 841 BCE, King Li of the Western Zhou (877 - 841 BCE) was deposed and forced into exile until his death. Power was held for 14 years by the Gonghe Regency. Hook, pp. 144-147; Li, 2018.

↳ (与采样地区外的族群)有暴力冲突吗：

– Yes

Notes: Yes and No, violent conflicts took place with clans/groups inside and outside the same region.

该宗教团体有确认入会的一般性程序/制度吗：

– Yes

↳ 与生俱来（成员身份在这种社会是默认的）：

– Yes

↳ 基于个人选择：

– Yes

↳ 由社会阶层赋予：

– Yes

↳ 由特定年龄阶段赋予：

– Yes

↳ 由性别赋予：

– Yes

↳ 由参与特定仪式赋予：

– Yes

↳ 由其它因素而赋予：

– Yes [specify]: Assigned by some other factors such as perhaps health conditions, literacy, marriage, tribes, other states besides the Western Zhou.

宗教团体有积极宣教、招募新成员吗：

– I don't know

宗教有官方的政治支持吗：

– Yes

Reference: Li, Feng. *Early China: A Social and Cultural History*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press 2013. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2013.

↳ 神职人员由政体出资供养吗：

– Yes

Notes: Some were possibly appointed by the Western Zhou kings and royal lineage into the emerging Zhou bureaucratization as LI Feng argues in his book, *Early China: A Social and Cultural History* (Cambridge University Press, 2013), chs. 6-7.

↳ 宗教基础设施由政体出资吗：

– Yes

Notes: For example, the Zhou royal temples in earlier six cities in Qiyi (Zhou, predynastic capital), Feng, Hao (Zongzhou), Zheng, Chengzhou (today's Luoyang), and Pang.

↳ 政体首脑和宗教领袖是同一个人吗：

– Yes

Notes: Yes and No. Unlike the Shang worshipping of a high God (Shangdi), the Western Zhou started to emphasize "heaven" and the Mandate of Heaven conferred to the Zhou kings to topple its Shang counterpart.

↳ 政治官员相当于宗教官员吗：

– No

↳ 宗教仪式是由政体强制执行的吗：

– Yes

Notes: Yes and No. The Western Zhou operated through the kings attempting to maintain control/ties with many other settlements/colonies/regional rulers.

↳ 政治律法和宗教法典大致重合：

– Yes

Notes: During the Western Zhou time, there was no strict polity legal code (perhaps in the sense of the later dynasty/first centralized state, the Qin) vs. religious code in the modern sense.

↳ 政体提供优惠的经济待遇(比如免税) :
– Yes

在该宗教中存在叛教的概念吗 :
– I don't know

大小和结构

在样本区域中的宗教团体信奉者人数(估计人口, 数字)
– Estimated population, numeric: 750000

Reference: Shaughnessy, Edward L.. "Historical Perspectives on the Introduction of the Chariot into China" 48, no. 1 (June 1988). <https://doi.org/10.2307/2719276>.

样本区域中的宗教团体的信奉者数量 (在样本区域人口中的百分比, 数字)
– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 90

宗教团体性质【请选其一】 :
– Large official religious group with smaller religious groups also openly allowed

在该宗教团体中是否存在被认可的领导者 :
– I don't know

Notes: These numbers and answers are all approximate and through inferences, because the exact number of population, priests, tribes, groups, kings' families and relatives are still unknown yet.

经典/经文

宗教团体有经典吗 :

经典是一个统称,指的是受到尊崇、与其它文本相比被认为具有特别的权威性和神圣性的文本。严格意义上经典指书写的文本,但是也存在“口述经典”(比如印度的吠陀经典)。

– Yes

↳ 它们是书面的吗 :
– Yes

Notes: Bronze and stone inscriptions, oracle bones, e.g.

↳ 它们是口述的吗：

– Yes

Notes: The Book of Songs, e.g.

↳ 经典的来源和一个（或一组）故事有关吗：

– Yes

↳ 由至高无上的神揭示：

– Yes

Notes: Heaven 上帝

Reference: Karlgren, Bernhard . ““on the Script of the Chou Dynasty.””. Museum of Far Eastern Antiquities Bulletin 8 (1936): 157-78.

<https://archive.org/details/Bulletin8/page/n269/mode/2up>.

↳ 由其他超自然生灵揭示：

– Yes

↳ 由至高无上的神启示：

– Yes

↳ 由其他超自然生灵启示：

– Yes

↳ 来源于神或半神半人：

– Yes

Notes: Allegedly, the script was created by the legendary figure Cangjie 倉頡.

↳ 来源于凡人：

– Yes

↳ 这一经典是否是可以改变：

– Yes

↳ 是否存在诠释经典的正式机构（比如被宗教团体或者政治领袖所授权的机构）：

– Yes

↳ 可以抛开这些机构来诠释经典吗：

– Yes

Notes: Depending on the circumstances, diviners, priests, the Overseer of Ritual Affairs (dazongbo 大宗伯) and the kings had the authority to interpret written scripts/scriptures with their own commentaries.

Reference: Kern, Martin. "Bronze Inscriptions, the Shangshu, and the Shijing: The Evolution of the Ancestral Sacrifice During the Western Zhou". In *Early Chinese Religion, Part One: Shang Through Han (1250 BC to 220 AD)*, 143-200. Leiden: Brill, 2009.

↳ 只有被正式批准的人员才可以诠释经典：

– No

↳ 是否存在一个专门被训练从事经典传布的特定群体：

– I don't know

↳ 是否存在一部结集的典籍经藏：

– Yes

Notes: The Western Zhou showed higher literacy in terms of written records as perhaps seen in the classic Zhouli (周禮 The Rites of the Zhou), the Book of Changes (I Ching), the Book of Songs, and the Book of Documents. Li Feng, *Early China: A Social and Cultural History* (2013). Also see <http://www.chinaknowledge.de/Literature/Classics/zhouli.html>

建筑，地理

是否存在纪念性的宗教建筑物：

– Field doesn't know

Notes: In general, only small and medium sized structures/tombs from the Western Zhou have been discovered in its capitals Feng and Hao near today's Xi'an, unlike its predecessor, the Shang in its capital Anyang. Xu Hong (许宏), et al., https://m.thepaper.cn/baijiahao_5001056?sdkver=e06426d6&clientprefetch=1 (published on November 20, 2019, accessed on March 30, 2024). <http://www.chinaknowledge.de/History/Zhou/zhou-art.html#architecture>. "The architecture of the Zhou can be divided into two types, namely the original Zhou style used in their homeland in the Zhouyuan Plain around Baoji, Fufeng and Qishan, and the other style found in the "metropolitan" area of Feng and Hao close to Xi'an. The word jing 京 "lofty, great" is of Zhou origin and was their word for residence or settlement where the Shang had used the word yi 邑 (Wu 1994: 196)." Excavations in today's Shaanxi 陕西 Province's Fufeng 扶風 uncovered the temple or palace complex of Fengchu erected on a pounded-earth platform and has a dimension of 45×32m. ... The complex thus corresponds to the model of the traditional siheyuan 四合院, a courtyard surrounded by four sides, with the main buildings located opposite to the entrance. The two courtyards of Fengchu were dewatered by canals of earthenware tubes. Before the entrance gate, a wall protected the complex from the influence of bad spirits."

有不同种类的宗教纪念性建筑物吗？

– Yes

↳ 陵墓

– Yes

Notes: Thus far, large Zhou royal tombs at Feng and Hao 豐鎬 (near today's Xi'an) have not been discovered yet. This forms a contrast with the famous royal tomb, Lady Good 好妇 in Anyang. Xu Hong (许宏), et al., https://m.thepaper.cn/baijiahao_5001056?sdkver=e06426d6&clientprefetch=1 (published on November 20, 2019, accessed on March 30, 2024).

↳ 公墓

– Yes

↳ 庙宇

– Yes

↳ 圣坛

– Yes

Notes: In terms of ancestor worship in the Western Zhou, there were altars or individual shrines that placed the soul tablets in the center rear altar (earlier ancestor), the right (King Wu) and left (King Wen) wings.

↳ 用于礼拜的标志性建筑

– Yes

Notes: Human and animal sacrifices and other offerings, besides bronze and stone inscriptions.

↳ 大规模集会点（庭院、广场等，用可见物或结构永久划分出来的场所）

– Yes

↳ 其它种类的宗教纪念性建筑物

– Yes [specify]: Underground tombs, tunnels, and surface structures

是否存在表征标志

– Yes

↳ 表征在哪里显示【多选】

– On persons

– At home

– Some public spaces

– All public spaces

Notes: The findings at the Sanxingdui三星堆 in Guanghan (廣漢), Sichuan Province include a

huge bronze figure, a large bronze head with protruding eyes. This points to other states and cultures in existence alongside the Shang and the Western Zhou periods, the bronze age of perhaps the Kingdom of Shu.

↳ 宗教团体的表征标志有明显特色吗

– Yes

↳ 眼睛（是否写实）

– Yes

↳ 超自然的存在(兽形)

– Yes

↳ 超自然的存在(地貌外形)

– Yes

↳ 超自然的存在(人形)

– Yes

↳ 超自然的存在(抽象的象征符号)

– Yes

↳ 对来世的描绘

– Yes

↳ 教义方面（比如，十字架、三位一体、密特拉教符号）

– Yes

Notes: 事死如事生

↳ 人类

– Yes

↳ 表征有其它特色：

– Yes

是否有专门的地点用于神圣行活动或者被认为是神圣的：

– Yes

- ↳ 神圣场地是否适应环境特点：
“环境特点”指的是风景、山水、罗盘方位等等的特征。
– Yes

有朝圣活动吗：
– I don't know

信仰

埋葬和来世

是否存在精神-肉体的区分

只有当人格（或意识）随肉体死亡而消亡时回答“否”。回答是并不一定意味着存在笛卡尔精神/肉体二元论，而只意味着人格（或意识）的一些要素在肉体死后尚存。

– Yes

- ↳ 精神 – 心灵被认为具有异乎其它身体部位的能力或特质
– Yes

Notes: During the Shang and Western Zhou times, soul-mind was considered to continue even after the body perished.

- ↳ 精神 – 心灵被认为是非物质的，在本体论上不同于身体
– No

- ↳ 其它心灵-身体关系：
– Yes [specify]: Spirit/ghost-body all needed to be treated well in afterlife.

对来世的信仰：

– Yes

Notes: It was general believed that bloodshed vitalized both the living and the dead, treating afterlife and this life the same.

- ↳ 该宗教团体对来世的空间位置有具体描述吗
– Yes

- ↳ 来世在这个世界之外的特定领域空间：
– Yes

在这个世界上的转世

– Yes

Notes: For instance, in some areas, it was believed that part of the soul (po 魄) of the deceased could come out of the dead body, and travel through doors or other openings, whereas the other part of the soul (hun) went to the netherworld. Lagerwey, 2008.

↳ 以人形转世：

– Yes

Notes: Lagerwey, 2008.

↳ 以动物／植物的形态转世：

– Yes

Notes: Lagerwey, 2008.

↳ 以非生物的形态转世：

– Yes

Notes: Lagerwey, 2008.

↳ 以非个体的形态转世（比如集体重生、部落、家族等等）：

– I don't know

↳ 和超越此生的因果机制有联系（比如，业力）：

– Yes

Notes: Heavenly spirits, terrestrial forces, and human ghosts were transcendental. There were divination inquiries to the dead kings of the Shang and Zhou by counting out stalks and establish one of the 64 hexagrams. Lagerwey, 2008.

↳ 这个世界中的其他形式的转世

– I don't know

对信众的遗体有特别处置吗：

– Yes

Notes: Although no large tombs of the Western Zhou kings have been discovered yet, it is likely that ornaments, some ointment, clothing and others were used to protect against the decay, please the dead, and perhaps confirm immortality. Loewe, 1999; Wilkinson, 2012.

↳ 火化

– I don't know

- ↳ 制成木乃伊
– I don't know
- ↳ 埋葬：
– Yes
 - ↳ 遗体被蜷屈 (腿部弯曲或身体蜷缩)
– Yes
 - ↳ 遗体被伸展(或躺或卧)
– Yes
 - ↳ 遗体竖立 (遗体以站姿安葬)：
– No
 - ↳ 遗体以其他方式安葬：
– I don't know
- ↳ 被食用：
– I don't know
- ↳ 暴露放置 (比如风干)：
– Yes
- ↳ 喂动物：
– Yes
- ↳ 二次埋葬：
– Yes
- ↳ 遗体再处理：
– Yes
- ↳ 其他强化 (就时间或资源的耗费而言) 处理方法 [请注明]
– Yes [specify]: Clothing and jewelry, e.g.

埋葬过程中或者墓穴中是否存在一起殉葬现象

– Yes

↳ 存在人类殉葬：

– Yes

↳ 团体外的人殉葬：

– Yes

↳ 团体内的人殉葬：

– Yes

↳ 其它人殉葬：

– Yes [specify]: Prisoners and war captives

↳ 存在动物一起殉葬

– Yes

Notes: Pigs, sheep, etc.

是否存在陪葬品：

– Yes

↳ 个人物品：

– Yes

↳ 有价值的物品：

– Yes

↳ 价值贵重（比如，金、玉、精工物品）：

– Yes

Notes: Bronze vessels

↳ 有些价值（某些值钱物品或者有用的物品陪葬）：

– Yes

↳ 其它有价值/珍贵物品陪葬：

– Yes [specify]: Bronze vessels and bells, and clay figures, e.g.

↳ 其他陪葬品：

– Yes

有正式的葬礼吗：

– Yes

↳ 树立纪念碑：

– Yes

↳ 葬于公墓：

– Yes

↳ 葬于家庭墓地或教堂地下室

– Yes

↳ 在家里（埋在房屋地下或者在有正常家庭活动的地方）

– Yes

↳ 其他正式的葬礼形式：

– Yes [specify]: Royal lineage cemetery

超自然存在

有超自然存在吗：

– Yes

↳ 有一个至上之神存在

– No

Notes: Compared to the Shang times, the Western Zhou in its middle and latter stage was inclined to believe in Mandate of Heaven and the bronze, stone and pottery vessels tended not to have many mysterious figures and beings. Some scholars argue for a ritual and cultural revolution during the Zhou.

↳ 过去人的灵魂是存在的：

– Yes

↳ 人类灵魂可以被看到

– Yes

↳ 人类灵魂可以用身体感触到：

– Yes

↳ 过去人的灵魂对这个世界有所认知：

– No

Notes: Yes and No. Although the Western Zhou peoples were allegedly not so much obsessed with the high God (Shangdi) and soul/spirit as the Shang royal families, their burial goods indicated the belief of treating the dead body and spirit the same as if they were alive in this world. 事死如事生

↳ 人类灵魂至上对这个世界能够有意施发因果效力：

– Yes

↳ 人类灵魂可以奖赏：

– Yes

↳ 人类灵魂可以惩罚：

– Yes

↳ 人类灵魂对这个世界有间接因果效应：

– Yes

↳ 人类灵魂对人生有记忆：

– Yes

↳ 人类灵魂展现出积极的情感：

– Yes

↳ 人类灵魂展现出负面的情感：

– Yes

↳ 人类灵魂有饥饿感：

– Yes

↳ 人类灵魂有/展现出一些其他特征：
– Yes [specify]: Legitimacy of governance and polity

↳ 人类灵魂和生灵沟通：
– Yes

↳ 在清醒状态下的日常生活中：
– Yes

↳ 在睡梦中：
– Yes

↳ 在被附体催眠状态中：
– Yes

↳ 通过占卜行为：
– Yes

↳ 只通过专业的宗教人士：
– Yes

↳ 只通过君主：
– Yes

↳ 其他与生灵的交流方式：
– Yes [specify]: Divination, weather and crops, e.g.

↳ 有非人类的超自然存在：
– I don't know

Notes: Yes and No. Archeological objects and some written inscriptions indicate the belief in some mysterious supernatural figures and beings.

↳ 有半人半神的存在：
– Yes

↳ 这些半人半神的存在可以被看到：
– Yes

- ↳ 这些半人半神的存在可以用肢体感触到：
 - Yes

- ↳ 半人半神的存在对这个世界有所认知：
 - Yes

- ↳ 半人半神的存在所知限于特定领域的人类事务：
 - Yes

- ↳ 半人半神的存在对于这个世界有意造成因果效应：
 - Yes

- ↳ 这些半人半神的存在可以奖赏：
 - Yes

- ↳ 这些半人半神的存在可以惩罚：
 - Yes

- ↳ 这些半人半神的存在对世界上有间接因果效应：
 - Yes

- ↳ 这些半人半神的存在展现出积极的情感：
 - Yes

- ↳ 这些半人半神的存在展现出负面的情感：
 - Yes

- ↳ 这些半人半神的存在有饥饿感：
 - Yes

- ↳ 这些半人半神的存在有/展现出一些其他特征：
 - Yes [specify]: Affecting political legitimacy, crops, weather, etc.

- ↳ 这些半人半神的存在和生灵沟通
 - Yes

- ↳ 在清醒状态下的日常生活中：
 - Yes
 - ↳ 在睡梦中：
 - Yes
 - ↳ 在被附体催眠状态中：
 - Yes
 - ↳ 通过占卜行为：
 - Yes
 - ↳ 只通过宗教专业人员：
 - Yes
 - ↳ 只通过君主：
 - Yes
 - ↳ 其他与生灵的交流方式：
 - Yes [specify]: Through divination, weather, crops, wars, etc.
- ↳ 宗教团体具有多种超自然存在：
 - Yes
- ↳ 以基于家庭模式的亲属关系编排：
 - Yes
 - ↳ 按照高下阶层编排：
 - Yes
 - ↳ 各自的权力是限于所属领域的：
 - Yes
 - ↳ 万神庙的其他组织方式：
 - Yes [specify]: Kinship, clan, tribes, lineage, divination, etc.

超自然监视

是否存在超自然的监视：

“超自然监视”是指超自然存在监视人类的行为以及或者思想，特别是涉及到社会准则或潜在性违规的情况。

– I don't know

超自然存在施加惩罚吗：

– Yes

↳ 超自然惩罚的来源或是动因是已知的吗：

– Yes

↳ 只由至上之神完成

– Yes

↳ 由许多超自然存在完成：

– Yes

↳ 由客观的因果定律来完成：

– Yes

↳ 由其他实体或其他方式完成【请注明】：

– Yes

↳ 超自然惩罚的存在原因是已知的吗：

– Yes

↳ 为了实现宗教的仪式-崇拜的信奉：

– Yes

↳ 为了强制实施团体准则：

– Yes

↳ 为了阻止自私自利：

– Yes

↳ 随机：
– Yes

↳ 其它【请注明】
– I don't know

↳ 超自然惩罚在来世施行：
– I don't know

↳ 超自然惩罚在今世施行：
– Yes

↳ 宗教团体非常强调今世的超自然惩罚：
– Yes

↳ 今世的惩罚包括噩运：
– Yes

↳ 今世的惩罚包括政治上的失败：
– Yes

↳ 今世的惩罚包括在战斗中失败：
– Yes

↳ 今世的惩罚包括农作物欠收或恶劣天气：
– Yes

↳ 今世的惩罚包括出游上灾祸：
– Yes

↳ 今世的惩罚包括轻微的感觉的不悦：
– Yes

↳ 今世的惩罚包括强烈的感觉的不悦：
– Yes

- ↳ 今世的惩罚包括疾病：
– Yes
- ↳ 今世的惩罚包括生育上出问题：
– Yes
- ↳ 今世的惩罚包括后代承受噩运：
– Yes
- ↳ 其它【请注明】
– Yes
Notes: Unknown matters

超自然存在赐予奖赏吗：

– Yes

- ↳ 超自然奖赏的来源/目的是已知的吗：
– I don't know
- ↳ 在来世赐予超自然奖赏：
– Yes
- ↳ 宗教团体非常强调来世的超自然奖赏：
– Yes
- ↳ 来世的奖赏包括轻微的感觉愉悦：
– Yes
- ↳ 来世的奖赏包括极度的感觉愉悦：
– Yes
- ↳ 来世的奖赏包括永恒的幸福：
– Yes
- ↳ 来世的奖赏包括转世为更高级生命形式：
– Yes

↳ 来世的奖赏包括投生到更高级的领域中：
– Yes

↳ 其它【请注明】
– Yes

Notes: Unknown matters

↳ 在今世赐予超自然奖赏：
– Yes

↳ 宗教团体非常强调今世的超自然奖赏：
– I don't know

↳ 今世的奖赏包括好运：
– Yes

↳ 今世的奖赏包括政治上的成功或权力：
– Yes

↳ 今世的奖赏包括在战斗的胜利：
– Yes

↳ 今世的奖赏包括和平或社会稳定：
– Yes

↳ 今世的奖赏包括好的收成或风调雨顺：
– Yes

↳ 今世的奖赏包括出行上一路顺风：
– Yes

↳ 今世的奖赏包括轻微的感觉愉悦：
– Yes

↳ 今世的奖赏包括极度的感觉愉悦：
– Yes

↳ 今世的奖赏包括更好的健康：
– Yes

↳ 今世的奖赏包括多子多孙：
– Yes

↳ 今世的奖赏包括子孙多福
– Yes

↳ 其它【请注明】
– Yes

Notes: Unknown matters

救世主/末世论

是否存在救世主信仰：
– No

存在某种末世论吗：
– I don't know

Notes: Perhaps, since there was a general concept and practice of treating death/post-life just like living during the time period. This meant luxurious burial and tombs with sacrifices and goods/objects. Each clan (氏族) and lineage (血统) could have different eschatology as well.

规范与道德现实

该宗教团体规定总体性的社会准则了吗：
– Yes

Notes: In the Book of Changes and the Rites of the Zhou, e.g.

该宗教团体存在传统和道德范畴的区分吗：
– Yes

↳ 这种区别的性质是什么：
– Present (but not emphasized)

Notes: For instance, the ideas about inheritance of the eldest son (in relation to younger brothers/sons) vs. filial treatment of mothers, in some situations.

↳ 宗教团体对道德规范有专门规定吗：

– I don't know

Notes: For instance, vague and discernable ideas of filial piety, familial relations, but this has to be dealt with in a case by case situation.

↳ 道德规范适用于：

– All individuals within society (excepting slaves, aliens)

该宗教团体是否有提倡的核心重要美德：

– I don't know

常规

会员费用和惯例

该宗教团体要求成员禁欲(完全禁绝性生活)吗：

– No

该宗教团体要求成员节制性行为(部分禁止性生活)吗：

– No

该宗教团体要求成员阉割吗：

– No

该宗教团体要求成员斋戒吗：

– I don't know

该宗教团体要求成员断除某些食物（对想吃的食物的禁忌）吗：

– I don't know

Notes: We know that the Zhou peoples emphasized/liked food more than wines seen in written ritualized practices and pottery, stone, and bronze vessels, compared to the jShang peoples (producing/using more wine vessels).

该宗教团体要求成员在身体上留下永久性疤痕或作疼痛的修整吗：

– I don't know

Notes: Slaves, war prisoners, and hostile tribal members were sacrificed.

该宗教团体要求成员忍受疼痛的身体姿势或暂时性的伤口吗：

– I don't know

Notes: Ibid.

该宗教团体要求成年成员的牺牲生命吗

“成年”在此指该文化中主位或本土的类别；如果此类别不同于主流西方定义中的超过18周岁的并且为他/她的行为负法律责任的人类，那么请在评论/来源中注明：以下文本框。

– Yes

↳ 外来人，奴隶：

– Yes

↳ 平民：

– Yes

↳ 精英阶层：

– Yes

↳ 其它：

– Yes [specify]: War captives

该宗教团体要求儿童成员的牺牲吗

“儿童”在此指该文化中主位或本土的类别；如果此类别不同于主流西方定义，请在评论/来源中注明：以下文本框。

– Yes

↳ 外来人，奴隶

– Yes

↳ 平民

– Yes

↳ 精英阶层

– Yes

Notes: We know that during the Zhou times, the urban settlements/cities in today's Luoyang had designated district/zone for the Shang peoples with much lower social and economic status. See Wang, Dong. Longmen's Stone Buddhas and Cultural Heritage: When Antiquity Met Modernity in China Lanham, Md.: Rowman & Littlefield, 2020, especially Chapter 1.

↳ 其它 [请注明]

– Yes [specify]: War captives and/or the Shang peoples, if not all.

Notes: Wang, Dong. Longmen's Stone Buddhas and Cultural Heritage: When Antiquity Met Modernity in China Lanham, Md.: Rowman & Littlefield, 2020, esp. Chapter 1.

该宗教团体要求成员自我牺牲（自杀）吗：

– I don't know

该宗教团体要求成员贡献出财产／昂贵的物品吗：

– I don't know

该宗教团体要求成员奉献出自己的时间吗（例如参加会议或仪式，常规祷告等）：

– I don't know

Notes: Probably yes for regular divination activities. See Keightley, David N. Public Work in Ancient China : A Study of Forced Labor in the Shang and Western Chou. Ann Arbor, MI: University Microfilms International, 1980.

该宗教团体要求成员承受身体上的风险吗：

– Yes

Notes: Keightley, David N. Public Work in Ancient China : A Study of Forced Labor in the Shang and Western Chou. Ann Arbor, MI: University Microfilms International, 1980.

该宗教团体要求成员接受道德戒律吗：

– I don't know

Notes: Perhaps. See Keightley, David N. "What Did Make the Chinese "Chinese"?. " Education about Asia, 2004, 17-23.

成为该宗教团体的成员会被组外成员边缘化吗：

– Yes

Notes: Yes and No because the Western Zhou was not a strictly defined religious group. Instead it was a country/state that consisted of fluid settlements/colonies that were tied together through marriages, loyalties, blood linkage, division of labor, etc.

该宗教团体要求成员参与小规模宗教仪式（私人的，家庭的）吗：

– Yes

表演间的平均时间间隔是多少（以小时计）：

这里表演指小型仪式。

– I don't know

该宗教团体要求成员参与大规模的宗教仪式吗：

比如，涉及两个或以上的家庭；包括有大规模的“典礼”和“节庆”。

— Yes

↳ 平均来说，大规模的宗教仪式有多少参与者聚集在一个地点：

— I don't know

↳ 表演间的平均时间间隔是多少（以小时计）：

这里表演指小型仪式。

— I don't know

↳ 是否存在正统性审查：

正统性审查是用于保证用常规方式阐释仪式的机制。比如，通过专业祭司或者其他系统的管理的显赫监督，诉诸于详细适当阐释的文本等等。

— I don't know

↳ 是否存在对仪轨规范性审查：

仪轨规范性审查是用于保证用常规方式阐释仪式的机制。比如，通过专业祭司或者其他系统的管理的显赫监督，诉诸于详细记载适当程序的文本等等。

— I don't know

↳ 参与包括完全同步的修行吗：

— Yes

Notes: Divination practices

↳ 使用酒精饮料吗：

— I don't know

除了仪式之外还有群内的的标示性符号吗：

比如，关于外表的特别改变，比如割礼、纹身、牺牲等等。

— I don't know

团体使用虚拟的亲族称谓吗：

— Yes

↳ 虚拟的亲族称谓是普遍的：

— I don't know

↳ 虚拟的亲族称谓是广泛的：
– I don't know

↳ 使用虚拟的亲族称谓，但不常见：
– I don't know

社会与机构

社会复杂程度

对宗教团体所属社会最恰当的描述为（请选其一）：
– A state

福利

该宗教团体提供制度化的救助饥荒的服务吗：
– Yes

饥荒救济是通过该宗教团体以外的机构提供给该团体信众的吗：
– I don't know

该宗教团体提供制度化的的贫困救济吗：
– I don't know

贫困救济是通过该宗教团体以外的机构提供给该团体信众的吗：
– I don't know

该宗教团体对年老体弱者有制度化的关怀吗：
– Yes

对年老体弱者制度化的关怀是通过该宗教团体以外的机构提供给该团体信众的吗：
– Yes

教育

该宗教团体为信众提供正规教育吗：
– No

Notes: There were royal schools, Xuegong 學宮. Ulrich Theobald,

<http://www.chinaknowledge.de/History/Zhou/zhou-admin.html#royaldomain>

正规教育是通过宗教团体以外的机构提供给团体信众的吗：

– No

Notes: There were royal schools in the Zhou settlements/colonies. Ulrich Theobald,
<http://www.chinaknowledge.de/History/Zhou/zhou-admin.html#royaldomain>

官僚机构

团体的信徒与团体内的官方机构有互动吗？

– Yes

Notes: See Li, Feng, 2013, esp. chs. 6-7.

宗教信众与其他官僚机构有互动吗：

– Yes

公共工程

该宗教团体储备公共食品吗：

– Yes

公共食品储备是通过该宗教团体以外的机构提供给该团体信众的吗：

– Yes

该宗教团体提供水资源管理（灌溉、防洪）吗：

– Yes

水资源管理是通过该宗教团体以外的机构提供给该团体信众的吗：

– Yes

该宗教团体提供基础设施吗：

– Yes

基础设施是通过该宗教团体以外的机构提供给团体信众的吗：

– Yes

纳税

该宗教团体课取税款或什一税吗：

— Yes

Notes: Ulrich Theobald, <http://www.chinaknowledge.de/History/Zhou/zhou-admin.html#legalsystem>

团体信众的税是由该宗教团体以外的机构来征收吗：

— Yes

Notes: Ulrich Theobald, <http://www.chinaknowledge.de/History/Zhou/zhou-admin.html#legalsystem>

强制

该宗教团体设有体制化的警务部门吗：

— Yes

Notes: According to transmitted sources, including The Book of Documents (尚書), The Book of Rites (左傳), and The Book of Rites (周禮). Poli, 2021. <http://www.chinaknowledge.de/History/Zhou/zhou-admin.html#legalsystem>

宗教团体的信众与外部体制下的警务部门有互动吗：

— Yes

Notes: Ulrich Theobald, <http://www.chinaknowledge.de/History/Zhou/zhou-admin.html#legalsystem>

该宗教团体设置体制化的法官吗：

— Yes

Notes: <http://www.chinaknowledge.de/History/Zhou/zhou-admin.html#legalsystem>

宗教团体的信众与外部体制下的司法系统有互动吗：

— Yes

Notes: Transmitted sources, see Ulrich Theobald, <http://www.chinaknowledge.de/History/Zhou/zhou-admin.html#legalsystem>

该宗教团体施加制度化的处罚吗：

— Yes

Notes: <http://www.chinaknowledge.de/History/Zhou/zhou-admin.html#legalsystem>

制度化的处罚包括死刑吗：

— Yes

Notes: Ulrich Theobald, <http://www.chinaknowledge.de/History/Zhou/zhou-admin.html#legalsystem>

↳ 制度化的处罚包括流放吗：

– Yes

Notes: Hook, 1991.

↳ 制度化的处罚包括体罚吗：

– Yes

Notes: <http://www.chinaknowledge.de/History/Zhou/zhou-admin.html#legalsystem>

↳ 制度化的处罚包括排挤孤立吗：

– Yes

Notes: <http://www.chinaknowledge.de/History/Zhou/zhou-admin.html#legalsystem>

↳ 制度化的处罚包括没收财产吗：

– Yes

Notes: <http://www.chinaknowledge.de/History/Zhou/zhou-admin.html#legalsystem>

宗教团体的信众承受宗教团体以外的体制下的处罚吗:

– Yes

Notes: <http://www.chinaknowledge.de/History/Zhou/zhou-admin.html#legalsystem>

↳ 制度化的处罚包括死刑吗：

– Yes

Notes: <http://www.chinaknowledge.de/History/Zhou/zhou-admin.html#legalsystem>

↳ 制度化的处罚包括流放吗：

– Yes

Notes: Hook, 1991

↳ 制度化的处罚包括体罚吗：

– Yes

Notes: <http://www.chinaknowledge.de/History/Zhou/zhou-admin.html#legalsystem>

↳ 制度化的处罚包括排挤孤立吗：

– Yes

Notes: <http://www.chinaknowledge.de/History/Zhou/zhou-admin.html#legalsystem>

↳ 制度化的处罚包括没收财产吗:

– Yes

该宗教团体有正式的法典吗：

– Yes

Notes: Ulrich Theobald, <http://www.chinaknowledge.de/History/Zhou/zhou-admin.html#legalsystem>: "Transmitted sources speak of a legal code of nine chapters (xingshu jiupian 刑書九篇) or "nine punishments" (jiu xing 九刑) of the early Zhou."

宗教团体的信众受制于外部体制下的法典吗：

– Yes

Notes: Ulrich Theobald, <http://www.chinaknowledge.de/History/Zhou/zhou-admin.html#legalsystem>: "Transmitted sources speak of a legal code of nine chapters (xingshu jiupian 刑書九篇) or "nine punishments" (jiu xing 九刑) of the early Zhou."

福利

该宗教团体有体制化的军事力量吗：

– Yes

该宗教团体有权力征兵吗：

– Yes

该宗教团体维持全职的军队吗（例如瑞士卫队）：

– Yes

该宗教团体维持一支常备军队吗：

– Yes

宗教团体的信众参加宗教团体以外机构提供的机制化的军事力量吗：

– Yes

宗教团体的信众受保护或受治于宗教图案以外机构提供的机制化的军事力量吗：

– Yes

书面语

该宗教团体有自己独特的书面语吗：

– Yes

Notes: Bronze, stone, and pottery inscriptions besides the written scripts on oracle bones from preceding times such as the Shang (circa 1600 BCE - 1046 BCE). An index of inscribed bronzes can be found in Li, Feng. *Landscape and Power in Early China: The Crisis and Fall of the Western Zhou 1045-771 BC*. Cambridge: University of Cambridge Press, 2006, pp. 387-389.

↳ 这种独特的书面语的使用仅限于宗教专职人员吗：

– No

团体信众能在宗教团体以外的体制中接触到非宗教专用的书面语吗：

– Yes

团体信众在宗教团体以外的体制下使用非宗教专用的书面语吗：

– Yes

日历

该宗教团体有正式的历法吗：

– Yes

Notes: Evidence shows that during the Shang and the Western Zhou, the calendar was of a simple agricultural lunisolar type, and the more complex version of the lunar calendar is still in use and observed. It tried to keep in step with the phases of the Moon. Hook, 1991, pp. 377-379.

该宗教团体的信众在宗教团体以外的体制下有正式的历法可用吗：

– Yes

Notes: A formal calendar was managed/controlled by the state government/offices. Hook, 1991.

食物生产

该宗教团体自产食物吗

– Yes

Notes: Food included grain, millet, rice, vegetables such as cabbage, fish, meat (pigs, dogs, horses, chickens, etc. were raised) and others.

Reference: Scott, James. *Against the Grain: A Deep History of the Earliest States*. New Haven, C.T.: Yale University Press, 2017.

Reference: Beckwith, Christopher. *Empires of the Silk Road: A History of Central Eurasia from the Bronze Age to the Present*. Princeton, N.J.: Princeton University Press, 2009.

↳ 请描述食物生产的形式/层级 [多选]：

– Gathering

- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Reference: Sterckx, Roel. *Food, Sacrifice, and Sagehood in Early China*. Cambridge University Press, 2011.

该宗教团体外的机构向团体信众提供食物吗：

– Yes

Notes: Hook, 1991, pp. 368-377.

请描述食物生产的形式/层级【多选】

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Patorialism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

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Entry/Answer References

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